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A Sydney Rock Oyster Haemolymph Shows Antimicrobial Properties to Mitigate Bacterial Infections

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ABSTRACT

The Sydney rock oyster (*Saccostrea glomerata*) is a native bivalve mollusk found in estuarine and coastal waters of Australia and holds significant ecological and commercial importance. As a filter-feeder, it is constantly exposed to microbial pathogens and relies on its innate immune system for protection. A major component of this defense is the haemolymph, which contains antimicrobial proteins and peptides. Recent studies have shown that haemolymph exhibits antibacterial activity against a range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, inhibits biofilm formation, and can enhance the effectiveness of conventional antibiotics. These properties highlight its potential as a natural source of novel antimicrobial agents. However, Sydney rock oysters are susceptible to diseases such as juvenile oyster disease (JOD), QX disease caused by *Marteilia sydneyi*, and herpesvirus infections, which threaten aquaculture productivity. Understanding haemolymph's antimicrobial properties offers potential strategies to mitigate bacterial infections and improve oyster health management.

Keywords:- Sydney rock oyster, *Saccostrea glomerata*, haemolymph, phases of industry development, antimicrobial activity, oyster diseases

INTRODUCTION

Antibiotic- Antibiotics are a class of medications used to treat and prevent bacterial infections by either killing the bacteria (bactericidal) or stopping their growth and reproduction (bacteriostatic). They work by interfering with specific, vital processes within bacterial cells and are not effective against viral infections like the common cold or flu.

Antibiotics are primarily classified based on their chemical structure and their mechanism of action. By Chemical Structure/Class Antibiotics within the same chemical class generally share similar properties, effectiveness, and potential side effects. Major classes include:

Correct use of antibiotics is crucial to effectively treat infections and prevent the development of antibiotic-resistant bacteria [1]. One of the top priorities for global public health is the research and development of newly discovered antibiotics. Antibiotics are the primary type of treatment for bacterial infections, which are a major cause of illness. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is developing quickly, which is reducing the efficacy.

Currently being used first-line antibiotics, yet the development of novel medications is severely lacking [2]. AMR is currently linked to almost five million deaths annually due to the rise in untreatable illness rates caused by drug-resistant bacteria [3].

Additionally, the majority of illnesses include mode of bacterial growth that can withstand high antibiotic doses [4]. In order to maintain the capacity to prevent and treat infectious diseases and to reduce overexposure to current antibiotics that encourage the development of resistance, it is crucial to find new compounds with novel mechanisms of action (i.e.,

structurally distinct from existing classes of antibiotics, able to prevent/disperse biofilms) [5]. The humoral immune systems of the majority of multicellular creatures contain a wide collection of tiny proteins known as antimicrobial proteins and peptides (AMPPs) [6,7]. As a result, there are several unusual sources of AMPPs with distinctive functions [8]. AMPPs have been traditionally thought to have simple kinetics and broad-spectrum activity, but new research indicates that they also have high specificity and a possibility for synergism, or when the combined therapy's effect is larger than the sum of its parts [9]. Antibiotic and AMPP synergies offer exciting opportunities for the application of combination medicines in clinical settings in the future.

The majority of examples of synergistic interaction have been found between antibiotics that inhibit the production of proteins and nucleic acids that must enter the cell to exhibit their bactericidal effects and AMPPs that alter the permeability of bacterial cell membranes. Exercise AMR development is unlikely and generally mild toxicity are further advantages [10]. It follows that AMPPs are regarded as one of the most promising pharmacological leads.

At least 35 other AMPPs are undergoing clinical assessment, and five AMPPs four produced from bacteria and one from invertebrates are presently being used as substitute antibiotics in clinical settings. Although people can also create AMPPs, non-human sources are favoured since isolation as a treatment could lead to the development of endogenous immune resistance. A lot of interest has been given to AMPPs from marine invertebrates, especially the Mollusca, which have developed high innate immunity that helps to make up for a Lack of acquired immunity.

Saccostrea Glomerata

The Sydney Rock Oyster (SRO), *Saccostrea glomerata*, is the source of a semi-purified HPLC-fractionated hemolymph protein extract (HPE) the recently study shows and found to have strong bactericidal/biofilm inhibiting activity against *Streptococcus pneumoniae* [12]. Here, our goal was to screen for a wider variety of bacterial pathogens, paying special attention to those that cause respiratory infections. To evaluate the synergistic effect of HPE and traditional antibiotics, combination studies were conducted. In order to establish therapeutic importance, we also looked into thermal stability and cytotoxicity.

DISTRIBUTION & INDUSTRY

• These oysters are **endemic to Australia** and occur naturally from Hervey Bay in Queensland down to

Wingan Inlet in Victoria.

• The main commercial industry is in New South Wales (NSW). In NSW, the Sydney Rock Oyster makes up ~90% of the oyster industry in that state.

• The industry is old: the cultivation of the Sydney Rock Oyster in NSW is one of the country's oldest aquaculture industries

• Farming methods: They use natural spatfall (baby oysters) plus hatchery spat increasingly. Grow-out systems include floating baskets, trays, etc. It typically takes ~3 ½ years to reach market (plate) size.

The native Australian oyster species is the Sydney rock oyster (*Saccostrea glomerata*) (SRO). Only estuaries along the coasts of New South Wales (NSW) and southeast Queensland are home to this kind of oyster (Fig. 1). Early European settlement along Australia's east coast is where the SRO industry first emerged.

However, there is proof that Australia's Aboriginal inhabitants collected and ate SROs long before European settlers arrived (Attenbrow 2002). Oyster banks and reefs suffered greatly until the 1870s as a result of the first settlers' uncontrolled collection of oysters and oyster shell. The establishment of laws governing oyster harvesting in Queensland in the 1860s and New South Wales in the early 1880s established the groundwork for the growth of a commercial oyster industry. (Oyster

Culture Royal Commission, NSW, 1877). Production peaked in the 1970s, and this industry saw phases of rapid expansion until the late 1970s. SRO production has been declining since the 1970s.

The Corresponding Author (p.schrobback@gmail.com) attributes this to rising production costs, public health and safety concerns related to estuary water contamination, and oyster disease outbreaks (White 2001).

It's questionable if the SRO business can withstand today's pressures and continue to be financially successful in its current structure. For society and policymakers, the SRO industry's future does present a difficult challenge. At one extreme, it is a historically significant enterprise, and as such, there is a case can be made for preserving the native oyster's cultivation on the basis of cultural and heritage values. On the other hand, the industry can decide to replace the SRO with non native oyster species, which are more desirable to grow commercially but could endanger the native species' long-term survival. The purpose of this study was to review the history, current state, and possible future of Australia's native SRO sector. Previous reviews of the SRO industry's history have varied in their level of depth.

The purpose of this study was to analyze the Australian native SRO industry's history, current state, and possible future directions. Ogburn et al. (2007), Smith (1985), Nell (2001), Lergessner (2006), O'Connor and Dove (2009), Ogburn (2011), Clarke (2013), and sources mentioned therein have all reviewed the history of the SRO industry in varying degrees of detail and scope. This study sought to identify the industry's developmental stages and provide an overview of the authors' results. Additionally, the more recent advancements in the industry that were not sufficiently covered in the earlier assessments were the subject of this study. Fishery managers and stakeholders, both present and future, may find information From the industry assessment and the discussion of the study conclusions essential as a foundation Management reviews.

Taste and Culinary Use

From a culinary-perspective: Sydney Rock Oysters are prized for their rich, creamy flavour with a slight iodine finish.

- **Size/weight:** Typically marketed around 40–60 g whole weight (shell + meat) though they may be larger in some cases.
- **Best season:** They are available year-round, with peaks from September to March (for their fullest condition), though good ones may be available other times
- **Storage & cooking:** When buying live/unopened, ensure shells are tightly closed or close when tapped; keep cool and consume quickly. Over-cooking will toughen the meat
- **Pairings:** They go well raw with lemon/lime or dressings; also work with bacon, breadcrumbs, garlic, herbs, Asian dressings

CONSUMPTION

Sydney rock oysters are best consumed when freshly shucked, but do have a good shelf life when kept whole. Unopened oysters can remain alive, ready to be shucked, for up to 14 days, provided they are kept at the correct temperature (10 to 20°C) and handled safely. Live Sydney rock oysters should not be placed on ice, until shucked for consumption.

ECOLOGY

Sydney rock oysters are capable of tolerating a wide range of salinities. They are usually found in the intertidal zone to 3 m (9.8 ft) below the low-water mark. Oysters are filter feeders, straining planktonic algae from the water. Birds, fish, stingrays, mud crabs, and starfish all eat Sydney rock oysters, with the Australian pied oystercatcher (*Haematopus longirostris*) being particularly fond of them. Selective breeding of farmed rock oysters has successfully bred for disease resistance to two protozoan diseases of oysters, namely, QX disease *Marteilia sydneyi* and winter mortality *Bonamia roughleyi* [19].

3.1 Growth and reproductive life cycle

Sydney rock oysters are "broadcast spawners", that is, eggs and sperm are released into open water where fertilisation occurs. Within hours of

fertilisation, the eggs develop into free-swimming planktonic larvae. The larvae swim in estuarine and coastal waters for up to three weeks, during which they develop transparent shells and retractable feet. The larvae then settle on clean substrates using their feet to find suitable sites. The larval foot is resorbed once the larva is attached. The shell darkens and the small animal takes on the appearance of an adult oyster. Growth rates vary with local conditions, but they generally reach 50 g (1.8 oz) in three years. Sydney rock oysters may change sex as they are female. . . during life. Many individuals start out as males and later change to female's size.

About 60% of primeating oysters are female. Selective breeding has reduced the time to market size from size from three to two years [20].

EXAMINING THE PHASES OF INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT

Before 17881, pre-European settlement

The evolution of the SRO sector can be divided into five phases (Fig. 2). The sections that follow will provide descriptions of each of these phases. Long before European settlers arrived on Australia's east coast, native oysters were mostly found growing on sizable intertidal and subtidal oyster banks and reefs (Smith 1985; Lergessner 2006). Shell midden archeological evidence dates back to around 1720 BP, demonstrating that Aboriginals in coastal communities regularly gathered and consumed native oysters in NSW's northern estuaries (Bailey 1975). Rising sea levels have probably obliterated evidence of Aboriginal utilization of this resource, which possibly dates back further (Attenbrow 2002). Additionally, it has been recommended that in order to recover oysters, Aboriginal groups should deposit shell debris in the estuary before the oyster breeding season. beds by offering a substrate for the capture of fresh oysters (Ogburn et al. 2007). Oyster shells were also utilized by the

Aboriginal people as fishhooks, portable tools for spear maintenance, and for various cutting and piercing purposes, according to shell deposits found at archeological sites (Attenbrow 2002). Because of the low human population density, the effects of the Aboriginal people on oyster populations prior to European settlement are regarded as comparatively benign (Bailey 1975; Attenbrow 2002) [21].

From the 1790s until the turn of the century.

The late 1700s saw the start of large-scale SRO gatherings. shortly after European settlers arrived in NSW, north of Sydney (Smith 1985). In the past, oysters were found in large quantities in the intertidal zone between high and low water marks (bank oysters) or four meters below the water mark (dredge oysters) (Smith 1985). A dredging basket that was operated from a boat was used to gather dredged oysters (Smith 1981; Smith 1985). According to Smith (1981, 1985), dredged oysters grow more quickly, have a better flavor, and fetch higher prices. Because bank oysters were collected from dead oyster shells and naturally existing oysters stuck to stones, harvesting them was easier (Smith 1981). Either from the ground or the oyster reefs, these oysters were hand-picked (Smith 1985). Oysters were consumed and utilized as a source of lime for cement manufacturing by the 1860s.

Fatty acid extracts show antimicrobial activity

A study by Karthikeyan et al. (2014) in *Annals of Clinical Microbiology & Antimicrobials* found that fatty acid derivatives extracted from *S. glomerata* (via ethyl acetate extract) exhibited in vitro antibacterial (and antifungal and antiviral) activity.

- Extracts inhibited bacteria such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Vibrio harveyi*, *V. parahaemolyticus*, *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Staphylococcus aureus*.

- GC-MS of the active fraction identified compounds such as n-hexadecanoic acid, 6octadecenoic acid, L-(+)-ascorbic acid 2,6-dihexadecanoate, stigmasterol, γ -sitosterol, etc.
- The study also showed antifungal (e.g., *Aspergillus* spp., *Candida albicans*) and antiviral (white spot syndrome virus in shrimp) activity.
- The authors note that further purification and mechanistic work was needed.
- A later article (SSRG IJAES 2020) also references the ethyl acetate extracts being more potent than hexane or methanol extracts in antimicrobial screening [27].

More recently, research at Southern Cross University (Australia) has found that proteins from the hemolymph of Sydney rock oysters can kill bacteria and *enhance* the effectiveness of conventional antibiotics.

- The proteins prevented and disrupted biofilms, which are a key barrier in bacterial infections.
- In combination with antibiotics, the oyster hemolymph proteins improved antibiotic efficacy by **2- to 32-fold** depending on the bacteria and antibiotic used.
- For example, they reported that with sub-MBC (minimum bactericidal concentration) doses of hemolymph protein + antibiotic, pathogens including *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were more effectively treated.

The research is still early (in vitro) and has not yet progressed to extensive animal or human trials

Mechanistic & Immune-Defence Insights

:Some work has looked at cellular immune defence mechanisms in the oyster, e.g., phenoloxidase-associated cellular defence against the parasite *Marteilia sydneyi* in *S. glomerata*, showing haemocyte

phagocytosis and melanisation responses. Whilst not purely antibacterial, these studies highlight that the oyster has innate immune mechanisms (important in considering its antimicrobial potential).

- One review/report also noted that hemolymph extraction and analysis has been standardised in *S. glomerata* (e.g., protocols for collecting hemolymph, etc.) which aids research.

OYSTER DISEASES

Since the middle of the 1800s, when overfishing and the degradation of natural oyster beds paved the way for the growth of oyster farming through Disease has been the main determinant of oyster population dynamics throughout Europe (Roch, 1999). The production of oysters worldwide is based almost exclusively on five species. Because of this, oyster farms are typically local monocultures that are susceptible to epizootic diseases. The majority of oyster diseases are brought on by protozoan parasites, with the exception of OsHV1 in Pacific oysters. The marine habitats used for oyster cultivation offer an optimal medium for the spread and survival of parasite protozoa because of steady temperatures, natural currents, and the presence of intermediate hosts. The two primary protozoan illnesses influencing Sydney rock oyster production Winter QX illness and mortality solely affect *S. glomerata*. It was once believed that the spread of these illnesses was facilitated by the movement of oysters across rivers for on-growing in the 1960s (Nell, 2003). The protist *Bonamia roughleyi*, formerly known as *Mikrocytos roughleyi* (Cochennec-Laureau et al., 2003), is the primary agent of Winter Mortality. This contains the parasite of a genus that frequently affects flat oysters in Europe. As the name implies, winter mortality is limited to the cooler southern range of Sydney rock oysters and primarily occurs during the colder months of June to August [29]. In impacted areas, fatalities of

up to 80% are typical. The most vulnerable oysters are those in their third winter, right before they reach market size (Smith et al., 2000). Transferring oysters to upstream waters, where lower salinities are believed to reduce susceptibility to *B. roughleyi* infection, is one of the current approaches used to manage the disease. A lot of farmers also sell their roosters before the

third winter when they are most susceptible to infection. However, because oysters in these cooler waters take longer to reach market size, growers in more southern locales rarely have this option (Smith et al. (2000).

New research indicates that Winter Mortality may be caused by pathogens other than *B. roughleyi*.

(A) The major oyster growing areas of Australia and the species farmed in those areas [Nell, 2003]

(B) Sydney rock oyster production grew steadily until the mid-1970's, when pressure from infectious disease epizootics cause damage or decline in the industry (Nell, 2003).]

According to Adlard and Wesche (2005), these studies have revealed that *M. sydneyi* is found in the vast majority of *S. glomerata*-growing estuaries on the NSW coast, even some that were previously believed to be parasite-free. Only seven of the approximately 40 estuaries where Sydney rock oysters are raised have seen outbreaks of QX illness.

CONCLUSION

The Sydney rock oyster (*Saccostrea glomerata*) is an ecologically and economically important species native to Australia. Beyond its value as a seafood delicacy, scientific studies reveal it is a promising natural source of antimicrobial and bioactive compounds. These compounds, found in its tissues and hemolymph, show potential for developing new treatments or antibiotic enhancers.

However, most of this research is still in early laboratory stages, and further studies are needed to confirm safety, effectiveness, and possible applications in medicine or biotechnology.

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